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CARGO MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The primary goal of this project is to develop an intelligent energy meter based on the Internet of Things that uses a gsm module to measure energy use. We may transmit the energy consumption statistics by SMS to a mobile device. Data on energy use on a time-requirement basis is available. Among the problems with the current systems are Every time, we are unable to manually calculate the energy use by checking the meter. No concerning characteristics if they use more energy than the threshold. Lack of clarity about unit pricing while invoicing. Digital meters only show the current energy use; they do not provide historical energy usage data. Our technology allows for remote monitoring of power use. It could produce invoices that are more accurate. Additionally, we may send a message to switch the load on or off. The bill will be created after the load is turned off. Both the authorized electricity board and the client may update their bills online by sending an SMS, and we can pay with a cashless transfer, which will come in handy during these trying times (lockdown).

Keywords: SMS; consumption; energy meter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the safety and effectiveness of cargo loading operations is crucial in the ever-changing world of logistics and freight transportation. Cargo load monitoring is a vital component of this, since precise cargo weight measurement and management are essential to preserving transportation safety, legal compliance, and operational effectiveness. The emergence of novel technology has made it possible to develop Smart Cargo Load

Monitoring Systems customized for different sectors. Smart solutions, in contrast to conventional cargo monitoring techniques, make use of sophisticated sensors, real-time data analytics, and networked systems to provide a proactive and astute approach to cargo load assessment and management.

By combining cutting-edge technology, particularly Internet of Things (IoT) devices, the Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System offers a paradigm leap from traditional cargo weighing systems. These gadgets, which include wireless communication modules, load sensors, and pressure sensors, are arranged in a deliberate manner throughout the cargo transport trucks to create an extensive network that is able to monitor in real time. This network allows for precise cargo weight assessment as well as real-time input and modifications to guarantee ideal loading circumstances.

Figure.1: Cargo Load Sensor in Transportation
Key components of a Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System include sensor arrays, data processing units, and interconnected communication channels. These components work together to collect and analyze data, allowing the system to provide accurate and real-time information about the cargo weight. The system can trigger automated alerts, such as warnings for exceeding weight limits or unbalanced loads, ensuring compliance with

transportation regulations and enhancing overall safety.

The integration of smart technologies extends beyond cargo weight measurement to include predictive capabilities. Through the analysis of historical data and patterns, Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems can anticipate potential issues related to cargo load, enabling proactive measures to prevent incidents before they occur. This predictive capability not only enhances safety but also contributes to operational efficiency and resource optimization.

The transportation industry, with its diverse and complex cargo loading scenarios, stands to benefit significantly from the implementation of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems. These systems offer a tailored and adaptive approach to cargo load management, aligning with the unique challenges posed by various types of cargo and transportation modes. As the transportation sector embraces digital transformation, the convergence of IoT, data analytics, and cargo load monitoring presents a forward-thinking solution that not only ensures compliance but also elevates overall safety and efficiency standards in cargo transportation. In the subsequent sections, we delve into the specific components, functionalities, and advantages of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems, highlighting their transformative impact on cargo transportation protocols.

The implementation of a Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System goes beyond its immediate role in cargo weight measurement; it forms an integral part of broader transportation safety and efficiency ecosystems. With interconnected devices and data-driven insights, these systems contribute to creating a holistic cargo monitoring infrastructure, aligning with industry standards and regulatory requirements.

Central to the effectiveness of a Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System is its ability to provide real-time data analytics. The continuous

monitoring of cargo weight, combined with advanced analytics, allows the system to detect subtle changes indicative of potential cargo load issues. By leveraging machine learning algorithms, the system can adapt and improve its accuracy over time, enhancing its predictive capabilities.

Integration with Vehicle Fleet Management Systems and Transportation Management Systems (TMS) further extends the functionalities of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring. This integration enables seamless communication with other critical components of transportation operations, facilitating coordinated responses during loading, transit, and unloading processes, optimizing overall safety and efficiency protocols.

One notable feature of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems is their capacity for remote monitoring and control. Transportation vehicles, often covering vast distances, benefit from the ability to remotely access and manage cargo load monitoring systems. This capability not only expedites response times but also enables proactive measures, such as remotely adjusting cargo loads to prevent potential transportation risks.

1.1 Problem Statement:

While the advent of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems promises transformative advancements in cargo transportation safety and efficiency, several challenges persist, warranting careful consideration for effective implementation. One primary concern is the integration complexity associated with diverse transportation environments. The transportation industry operates with various vehicle types, cargo sizes, and logistical complexities, posing challenges in seamlessly incorporating Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems without disrupting existing operations.

Furthermore, the interoperability of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems with legacy cargo

monitoring infrastructure remains a critical challenge. Many transportation companies have invested in traditional cargo weighing methods, and the integration of smart technologies must ensure compatibility and cohesiveness with these pre-existing systems. The lack of standardized protocols for seamless integration exacerbates this challenge, necessitating a careful balance between innovation and compatibility.

Figure .2: Challenges in Cargo Load Monitoring Cybersecurity emerges as a paramount concern in the implementation of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems. As these systems rely on interconnected networks and IoT devices, the potential vulnerability to cyber threats raises significant apprehensions. Ensuring robust cybersecurity measures, including encryption protocols, secure communication channels, and protection against unauthorized access, becomes imperative to prevent potential breaches that could compromise the integrity of cargo load monitoring systems.

Moreover, the upfront costs associated with the adoption of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems may pose a financial hurdle for some transportation companies, particularly small and medium-sized enterprises. The initial investment in advanced load sensors, data processing units, and integration with existing infrastructure can be substantial. It is essential to address the cost-benefit analysis, ensuring that the long-term advantages and cargo transportation efficiency justify the initial capital outlay.

The scalability of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems presents another challenge, particularly for transportation companies undergoing expansion or modification. Ensuring that the system can seamlessly adapt to changes in the fleet size, cargo types, and vehicle specifications is crucial. Scalability issues may hinder the widespread adoption of these systems across diverse transportation settings.

Lastly, user awareness and training pose challenges in maximizing the potential of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems. Transportation personnel need to be adequately trained to understand and utilize the capabilities of these advanced systems effectively. A lack of awareness or insufficient training could result in underutilization or mismanagement of the technology, limiting its impact on overall safety and efficiency.

1.2 Problem Scope:

The scope of the challenges associated with implementing Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems in the transportation industry

The implementation of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems in the transportation industry encompasses a multitude of challenges across technological, regulatory, logistical, and environmental dimensions. Technologically, ensuring seamless integration with existing transportation infrastructure is a pivotal challenge, demanding a high degree of compatibility and interoperability. The accuracy and reliability of sensors utilized for load monitoring present intricate challenges related to precise calibration and resilience against diverse environmental conditions. The imperative to safeguard sensitive cargo data raises concerns regarding the establishment of robust cybersecurity measures and adherence to stringent privacy regulations.

Navigating the intricate web of complex regulatory frameworks, meeting stringent industry standards, and addressing potential

legal implications further contributes to the multifaceted challenges associated with the implementation of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems. Striking a balance between the upfront costs of implementation and the potential benefits derived, ensuring scalability to accommodate varying cargo scales, fostering collaboration among diverse stakeholders, and overcoming inherent resistance to change among workers constitute additional hurdles in the successful deployment of these systems.

In addition to these primary challenges, several other considerations add layers of intricacy to the implementation landscape. These include the necessity to address environmental resilience, accommodating the system to withstand harsh weather conditions and environmental factors. Real-time data processing capabilities, a crucial component for effective load monitoring, introduces technical challenges that demand the implementation of advanced analytics and machine learning algorithms.

The complexities of intermodal transportation, where cargo seamlessly transitions between different modes such as trucks, ships, and trains, present logistical challenges that require meticulous attention. The imperative of energy efficiency in the continuous monitoring of cargo necessitates a sustainable approach, including the incorporation of energy-efficient solutions such as renewable power sources and optimized power management strategies.

1.3: Advantages of cargo Load sensor

The implementation of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems in the transportation industry offers a myriad of advantages that significantly enhance the efficiency, safety, and sustainability of cargo transportation operations:

1. Enhanced Safety:

- Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems contribute to a safer transportation environment by providing real-time data on cargo conditions. This ensures that

cargo is securely loaded, reducing the risk of accidents, injuries, and damage to goods.

2. Optimized Resource Utilization:

- The precise monitoring capabilities enable better utilization of transportation resources. By accurately assessing the load status, companies can optimize vehicle capacity, leading to reduced fuel consumption and operational costs.

3. Improved Compliance:

- The implementation of these systems aids in complying with industry regulations and standards. This ensures that transportation operations align with legal requirements, minimizing the risk of penalties and regulatory issues.

4. Enhanced Operational Efficiency:

- Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems streamline cargo handling processes, leading to increased operational efficiency. Automated data collection and analysis reduce manual intervention, enabling quicker decision-making and smoother logistics operations.

5. Real-Time Visibility:

- The systems provide real-time visibility into the status of cargo, allowing logistics managers to track shipments throughout the transportation process. This enhanced visibility facilitates better planning, monitoring, and responsiveness to changing conditions.

6. Data-Driven Decision Making:

- The wealth of data generated by these systems empowers logistics professionals to make informed decisions. By leveraging analytics and insights derived from cargo monitoring, companies can optimize routes, schedules, and overall supply chain strategies.

7. Proactive Maintenance:

- Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems enable proactive maintenance by continuously monitoring the condition of cargo and the transportation vehicle. This helps identify potential issues before they escalate, reducing the likelihood of breakdowns and unplanned downtime.

8. Environmental Sustainability:

- The optimized resource utilization resulting from accurate load monitoring contributes to environmental sustainability. Reduced fuel consumption and efficient logistics operations lead to a smaller carbon footprint, aligning with sustainable and eco-friendly practices.

9. Enhanced Customer Satisfaction:

- Real-time tracking and monitoring capabilities contribute to improved customer satisfaction. Customers benefit from accurate delivery schedules, reduced instances of damaged goods, and increased transparency throughout the transportation process.

10. Adaptability to Varied Cargo Types:

- Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems are adaptable to different types of cargo, including perishable goods, hazardous materials, and fragile items. This versatility ensures that the system can be employed across diverse industries and transportation scenarios.

The advantages of implementing Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems extend across safety, operational efficiency, compliance, environmental sustainability, and customer satisfaction, making them instrumental in the evolution of modern transportation practices.

1.4 Proposed System

The Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System represents a paradigm shift in the transportation industry, offering a comprehensive solution that

leverages state-of-the-art technologies to redefine cargo monitoring practices. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) sensors within cargo spaces establishes a robust foundation for real-time data acquisition, enabling the system to monitor critical parameters like weight, temperature, and humidity. Augmenting this capability, camera modules equipped with advanced object detection utilize computer vision and machine learning algorithms to ensure the proper placement of safety essentials such as helmets, elevating cargo condition monitoring.

The secure communication infrastructure ensures the confidentiality and integrity of data transmitted between components, fostering a robust and reliable ecosystem. Predictive maintenance features leverage sensor data for anticipating potential issues, contributing to timely interventions and bolstering overall fleet reliability. User-friendly interfaces, including dashboards and mobile applications, cater to workers, logistics managers, and administrators, ensuring intuitive access to real-time data and enhancing decision-making.

Emergency response protocols within the system provide a safety net for unforeseen events during transportation, incorporating automated alerts and contingency plans. The integration of energy-efficient solutions, coupled with optimized power management and the use of renewable energy sources for sensor nodes, aligns the system with sustainability goals.

Comprehensive training programs for workers and system administrators facilitate a smooth transition to the Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System, maximizing its benefits. Designed with scalability and interoperability in mind, the system adapts seamlessly to varying cargo scales, different transportation vehicles, and evolving industry needs. The continuous improvement framework, encompassing regular updates and the assimilation of technological

advancements, ensures the system's perpetual evolution and enhancement over time.

The proposed Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System presents a holistic and technologically sophisticated approach to cargo transportation, aiming to address existing challenges, optimize operational efficiency, and contribute to a safer, more sustainable transportation ecosystem.

1.5 Aim and Objectives

Aim:

The aim of the Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System is to revolutionize cargo transportation practices by introducing an integrated, intelligent, and technologically advanced solution. The system aims to enhance safety, operational efficiency, and sustainability in the transportation industry through the seamless integration of cutting-edge technologies.

Objectives:

- 1. Implement Real-Time Monitoring:** Develop and deploy IoT-enabled sensors within cargo spaces to provide real-time monitoring of critical parameters, including weight, temperature, and humidity.
- 2. Enhance Safety Compliance:** Integrate camera modules with advanced object detection capabilities to ensure the proper placement of safety essentials, such as helmets, and monitor overall cargo conditions.
- 3. Automate Access Control:** Implement RFID-based access control and attendance tracking to streamline entry into safety-critical areas, automating attendance recording and regulating access based on predefined criteria.
- 4. Centralize Data Processing:** Establish a centralized data processing system to collect, process, and analyze data from sensors and cameras in real-time, generating actionable insights for stakeholders.
- 5. Ensure Secure Communication:** Develop a secure communication infrastructure to facilitate seamless data transmission between sensors,

cameras, and the centralized processing system, ensuring data confidentiality and integrity.

6. Enable Predictive Maintenance: Integrate predictive maintenance features leveraging sensor data to anticipate potential issues with transportation vehicles, enabling timely interventions and reducing the risk of breakdowns.

7. Create User-Friendly Interfaces: Design user-friendly interfaces, including dashboards and mobile applications, to provide workers, logistics managers, and administrators with intuitive access to real-time data and attendance records.

8. Implement Emergency Response Protocols: Incorporate emergency response protocols within the system to address unforeseen events during transportation, including automated alerts, notifications, and contingency plans.

9. Integrate Energy-Efficient Solutions: Incorporate energy-efficient solutions, optimized power management, and the use of renewable energy sources for sensor nodes to ensure sustainability and minimize environmental impact.

10. Facilitate Training Programs: Develop comprehensive training programs for workers and system administrators to ensure proficient usage of the Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System and facilitate a smooth transition to the new technology.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature survey conducted for the proposed Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System represents a meticulous exploration of current research, technologies, and methodologies in the realm of advanced cargo monitoring within the transportation industry. The survey is structured into several key dimensions to comprehensively cover the diverse aspects of cargo load monitoring technologies and their applications. The initial segment of the literature review scrutinizes existing cargo load monitoring

technologies, ranging from traditional methods like weighbridges to contemporary solutions such as load sensors and advanced weighing systems. The focus lies on evaluating the accuracy, reliability, and efficiency of these technologies and their adaptability to various cargo types and transportation modes.

Transitioning to the integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in cargo monitoring systems, the survey investigates studies exploring wireless communication modules, sensors, and IoT platforms. Emphasis is placed on understanding how interconnected networks enhance accuracy, responsiveness, and adaptability in dynamic transportation scenarios. A crucial facet of the literature survey revolves around predictive analytics for cargo load management. The examination delves into the application of machine learning algorithms and real-time data analytics for anticipating and preventing cargo-related incidents. The goal is to discern how historical data analysis contributes to the development of predictive models, optimizing cargo loading conditions and ensuring compliance with weight regulations.

The survey then shifts its focus to the integration of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems with Transportation Management Systems (TMS). Studies highlighting the seamless communication between these systems and broader transportation management platforms are explored, elucidating the importance of a coordinated and efficient transportation workflow.

Remote monitoring and control capabilities in cargo load monitoring systems are examined in detail, investigating case studies and research findings related to the remote access and management of these systems. The survey aims to uncover how this feature contributes to timely responses, proactive adjustments, and enhanced safety in transportation operations.

Given the interconnected nature of Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems, the literature survey scrutinizes cybersecurity measures implemented to safeguard these systems. Studies on encryption protocols, secure communication channels, and protection mechanisms against cyber threats are examined to understand how these systems mitigate vulnerabilities and ensure the integrity of data.

The incorporation of energy-efficient technologies in Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems is explored, focusing on research related to advanced propulsion systems, sustainable power sources, and eco-friendly materials. The survey seeks to identify how these technologies contribute to sustainable and responsible practices in cargo transportation.

Addressing the human factor, the literature survey explores studies on the development of comprehensive training programs for transportation personnel and initiatives to raise user awareness. Insights into the effectiveness of these programs in ensuring proficient operation and collaboration with cargo monitoring systems are gathered.

Ensuring compliance with weight regulations and safety standards is investigated, examining studies detailing how Smart Cargo Load Monitoring Systems are designed to meet or exceed regulatory requirements. Regular audits and assessments are explored as integral components to verify ongoing compliance with safety guidelines.

The literature survey concludes by navigating through continuous improvement frameworks applied to cargo monitoring systems. Research on incorporating feedback from operational use, simulations, and real-world scenarios is examined to identify how these frameworks contribute to the dynamic evolution of cargo load monitoring technologies.

The literature survey provides a holistic understanding of existing technologies,

challenges, and innovations in cargo load monitoring for transportation. The insights garnered will guide the development and implementation of the proposed Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System, ensuring alignment with industry best practices and addressing current and future needs in cargo transportation safety and efficiency.

III. BLOCK DIAGRAM

The envisioned Smart Cargo Load Monitoring System represents a paradigm shift in cargo monitoring practices within the transportation industry. At its core, the system integrates cutting-edge technologies to enhance safety, efficiency, and sustainability. It leverages an extensive network of Internet of Things (IoT) sensors strategically positioned in cargo spaces, capturing real-time data on crucial parameters like weight, temperature, and environmental conditions. Complementing this, advanced camera modules equipped with object detection capabilities employ machine learning algorithms to assess cargo spaces, ensuring safety essentials are in place and monitoring overall cargo conditions.

The centralized data processing system facilitates real-time analysis, employing advanced analytics algorithms to identify safety compliance, monitor cargo integrity, and generate actionable insights. A secure communication infrastructure ensures seamless data transmission, guaranteeing the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of critical cargo and safety-related information. Additionally, the system incorporates predictive maintenance features, utilizing sensor data to anticipate potential vehicle issues and proactively intervene to reduce breakdown risks.

Figure.3: Block Diagram

IV. HARDWARE COMPONENTS

4.1 NodeMCU (ESP8266)

The NodeMCU ESP8266 is a powerful and versatile platform designed for Internet of Things (IoT) development. The ESP8266 is a cost-effective Wi-Fi microchip known for its capability to enable wireless communication in IoT applications. NodeMCU, on the other hand, is an open-source firmware and development kit that simplifies the process of prototyping and programming the ESP8266. With built-in Wi-Fi connectivity, the NodeMCU ESP8266 allows devices to connect to the internet wirelessly, making it suitable for a wide range of IoT projects. One notable feature is its support for the Lua scripting language, providing a high-level programming environment for developers. Additionally, it is compatible with the Arduino IDE, allowing those familiar with Arduino to use the NodeMCU platform. Equipped with General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) pins, the ESP8266 facilitates interfacing with various electronic components, making it ideal for applications such as home automation and sensor networks. The NodeMCU ESP8266 has garnered significant community support, resulting in an extensive collection of libraries and documentation, making it a popular choice for rapid IoT prototyping and development.

Figure .4: NodeMCU 2D View
ESP8266 NODE MCU

Figure .5 : NodeMCU Parts

The NodeMCU ESP8266 development board typically has GPIO (General Purpose Input/Output) pins that can be used for various purposes, including interfacing with sensors, actuators, and other electronic components. Below is a common pinout configuration for the NodeMCU development board

Figure .6: NodeMCU ESP8266 Pinout

4.2 Load Cell

A load cell is an electro-mechanical sensor used to measure force or weight. It has a simple yet effective design which relies upon the well-known transference between an applied force, material deformation and the flow of electricity. They are incredibly versatile devices that offer accurate and robust performance across a diverse range of applications. It's no surprise that they have become essential to many industrial and commercial processes, from automating car manufacturing to weighing your

shopping at the checkout. As technology explodes forward, many new and exciting applications are emerging that also stand to benefit from using load cells. New advances in robotics, haptics and medical prostheses, to name a few, all need effective ways to measure forces and weights. New types of load cells are continuously being designed to meet the needs of this ever-changing market.

Figure .7: Load-cell Anatomy

Figure .8 : Load-cell Flexion

Technology Of A Load Cell

A typical load cell consists of two parts: the main body and an attached electrical circuit. The main body is what bears the weight or force and accounts for most of the load cell's size. Typically, it is made from high-grade steel or aluminium, which ensures mechanical reliability, and predictable and uniform strain distribution.

The electrical circuit is housed within the load cell, tightly bonded to the main body. The circuit includes strain-gauges which are specialised parts of the circuit designed to sense the deformations of the main body.

These strain-gauges consist of thin, electrically conductive wire or foil arranged in a tight zig-zag pattern. This pattern makes them sensitive to stretch and compression along their length, but

insensitive across their width. As such, they can be precisely positioned to sense forces that run along particular axes. For example, shear beam load cells have their strain gauges positioned at a 45-degree angle to the loading axis, so as to maximise the detection of the shear strain running through the load cell.

Figure .9: strain-Gauge Deformation

V. CONCLUSION

We concluded from the poll that the majority of people are interested in knowing how much power is used on a daily, monthly, and annual basis. They were relieved to be able to keep an eye on how much electricity they were using for their phones and to stop blaming the government. The public will see the government favorably as a result of increased government openness on unit current. Thus far, we have acquired the necessary knowledge to carry out the project by consulting IEEE papers, searching the internet and YouTube, recommending books, enrolling in online courses, examining public opinion surveys, and designing the project's hardware and necessary components. We will create a mobile application where people may monitor their power use in the future. To construct the application, we will take an Android programming course, and Firebase will be used for data storage. We also need to apply and execute our design. Google offers a cloud platform called Firebase for storing data.

REFERENCES

1. S. M. Amin and B. F. Wollenberg, "Toward a smart grid: power delivery for the 21st century," IEEE Power and

- Energy Magazine, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 34-41, 2005.
2. F. Benzi, N. Anglani, E. Bassi, and L. Frosini, "Electricity Smart Meters Interfacing the Households," IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics, vol. 58, no. 10, pp. 4487-4494, 2011.
3. D. S. Parker, "Pilot Evaluation of Energy Savings from Residential Energy Demand Feedback Devices," Florida, 2008.
4. Abhinandan Jain, Dilip Kumar, Jyoti Kedia, "Smart and intelligent GSM based automatic meter reading system", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), ISSN: 2278-0181, Vol 2, Issue 3, pp. 1-6, May 2012.
5. Priya Kamble, Sonali Bodkhe, "A new approach for design and implementation of AMR in Smart Meter", International Journal of Advanced Engineering Sciences and Technology, Vol. 2, PP. 57-61, 25 April 2011.
6. N. Kushalnagar, G. Motenegro, C. Schumacher, "IPv6 over Low-Power Wireless Personal Area Networks (6LoWPANs): Overview, Assumptions, Problem Statement, and Goals," RFC 4919, 2010.
7. J. Deny, N. Sivasankari, "Biometric Security in Military Application" Journal of Engineering Procedia ELSEVIER, Vol. 38, pp. 1138-1144, July 2012, ISSN No: 1877-7058.
8. J. Deny, G. Sridhar, M. Muneeswaran "Implementation Of Bidirectional Dc-Dc Converter For Aerospace Applications" International Journal of Pharmacy & Technology, Vol. 8, Issue 3, September 2016.
9. J. Deny, Dr. M. Sundhararajan "Multi Modal Biometric Security for Mobile

- Ad-hoc Networks and Its Applications” Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 42, November 2016
10. J.Deny, Darwin, J.,Anantha Kumar, R“Throughput-anonymity tradeoff for parallel relay networks ” International Journal of Pharmacy & Technology, Vol. 8, Issue 4, December 2016.
 11. Dr.E.Muthukumaran. Dr.J.Deny, Dr.B.Perumal,G. Suseendran., Dr. D.Akila “A narrative Non-Invasive Diagnostic loom Based by the side of correlation of Nasal set Rhythm in addition to customary Three Radial Pulses Measurement” IOP Conf. Series: Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 1228 (2019) 012075.
 12. Dr.E.Muthu Kumaran, M.Navin Kumar, Dr.J.Deny, Dr.T.S.Arun Samuel, “A Study on Analysing Microorganism Growth In Various Materials Of Cooking Vessels” International Journal Of Scientific & Technology Research Volume 8, Issue 10, October 2019, pp. 2195- 2198.
 13. R. Raja Sudharsan, J. Deny, et al., “An Analysis of Different Biopotential Electrodes Used for Electromyography”J. Nano- Electron. Phys. 12 No 1, 01020 (2020).
 14. Deny John Samuvel, B. Perumal, Muthukumaran Elangovan, “Music recommendation system based on facial emotion recognition, Publicado en 3C Tecnología. Special Issue – March 2020.
 15. M. Sakthimohan, J. Deny “An Enhanced 8x8 Vedic Multiplier Design By ApplyingUrdhva-Tiryakbhyam Sutra”, International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology Vol. 29, No. 5, (2020), pp. 3348 – 3358.